

ARE DECLINES IN INSECTS PUTTING UK BIRDS AND BATS ON RATIONS?

Key messages

- ▣ Some insects which are key food resources for bird and bat species are in decline in the UK.
- ▣ There are links between moth abundance and changes in populations of blue tits.
- ▣ The impacts of insect change on a range of bird and bat species are mixed, with some birds and bats seemingly unaffected by insect declines while those with specialized diets, or stronger reliance on insects during breeding, showing evidence of being impacted by insect change.

Challenge

There is convincing evidence of widespread declines in many insect species in the UK. Insects are the main food for numerous animals (e.g. bats, and many birds) and part of the diet of others. Therefore, there is concern that insect declines could have knock-on repercussions on other species and the wider health of ecosystems.

Previous studies have suggested that insect decline might cause local decreases in the populations of animals that eat them (insectivores). However, these links have not been investigated at the regional or national scale. The **DRUID project** aimed to fill this gap and assess if insect declines are having direct impacts on UK populations of a range of bird and bat species.

Figure 1. Insectivores and their insect food. Blue Tits feed on Winter moth larvae and other Lepidoptera during breeding season, and common Pipistrelle Bats feed on many fly species. Clockwise from left to right: Winter Moth larvae (photo by Dave Green), non-biting midge (photo by Jean & Fred CC BY-SA 3.0), common pipistrelle (photo by Barracuda1983 CC BY-SA 3.0), Blue Tit (photo by Francis Franklin CC BY-SA 3.0).

Our approach

We used citizen-science data from several standardised UK monitoring schemes that measure the changing populations of: butterflies (**UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme**), moths (**Rothamsted Insect Survey**), beetles (**Environmental Change Network**), freshwater insects (**Environment Agency**), birds (**RSPB/BTO/JNCC Breeding Bird Survey**) and bats (**National Bat Monitoring Programme**). These schemes provide decades of abundance data from different locations across the UK that can be combined to assess how insect change impacts local populations of insectivores.

A major challenge in such analysis is to try to determine whether declines in insectivores are caused by declines in its insects, or whether both populations are declining for another reason such as habitat destruction or climate change (Figure 2). To disentangle such factors we designed statistical models that aimed to control for shared responses to local habitat quality and factors such as yearly weather.

Figure 2. Population declines for insects and insectivorous vertebrates may be driven by shared responses to the same underlying threats (solid arrows) leading to parallel (correlated) declines, or there may be a direct effect of changing insect abundance on insectivores (dashed arrow). DRUID aimed to quantify the direct effect of insect change using novel methods.

Key findings

We found that UK blue tit populations were linked to yearly fluctuations in moth abundance, and to moth population changes over longer periods (Figure 3). Having taken the shared effects of environmental factors into account, these results suggest that changes in blue tit populations were driven by moth abundance, indicating that insect declines can directly impact bird populations at the national scale.

Figure 3. The relationship between Blue Tit population changes and moth abundance after controlling for other factors, such as site level variation and the previous year’s population size. The central panel shows Blue Tit population change compared to annual moth abundance, while the side panels show the effect of individual moth species change on Blue Tit numbers (clockwise from top-left Winter Moth (*Operophtera brumata*), Mottled Umber (*Erannia defoliaria*), Northern Winter Moth (*Operophtera fagata*), and Dun-bar (*Cosmia trapezina*) - four moth species that are identified as key food resources for blue tits. Note: values are on a standardised scale. Moth photos provided by Dave Green.

Extending this approach, we examined trends for five birds (Blue Tit, Great Tit, Grey Partridge, Skylark, Corn Bunting), five bats (Common Pipistrelle, Soprano Pipistrelle, Noctule, Serotine, Daubenton’s Bat), and their insect food. While insects and birds had generally declined across several spatial scales in the UK, insectivorous bats were mainly stable (Table 1).

Table 1. Trends in abundance across different spatial scales within the UK. ↘ are significant declines, → is no change, and ↗ are significant increases. The time-period varies between the surveys with the moths having the longest running data (1968-2017).

Taxa	100km	50km	10km
Birds			
▪ Blue tit	↘	↘	↘
▪ Great tit	↘	↘	↘
▪ Corn bunting	↘	↘	↘
▪ Grey partridge	↘	↘	↘
▪ Skylark	↘	↘	↘
Bats			
▪ Common pipistrelle	→	→	→
▪ Soprano pipistrelle	→	→	↗
▪ Noctule	→	→	→
▪ Serotine	→	→	→
▪ Daubenton’s bat	→	→	→
Insects			
▪ Moth index	→	→	↘
▪ Butterfly index	↘	↘	↘
▪ Diptera index	↘	↘	↘
▪ Beetle index	↘	-	-

In addition to repeating our previous results for blue tit, we also found evidence of direct links between insect abundance and population change great tit, grey partridge, and Daubenton's bats. However, we did not find conclusive evidence of direct effects of insect prey abundance for the other bird and bat species. That does not mean that there are no links in these cases, but that we did not find conclusive evidence in our research.

Implications

INSECT DECLINES

Consistent with many other studies, our analysis found that the amount of insect food available for insectivores in the UK has declined. These declines can impact animals higher up the food chain and also affect a range of other ecosystem functions such as pollination.

UNEVEN EFFECTS ACROSS SPECIES

In the UK, we found links between the populations of some birds (blue tit and great tit) and bats (Daubenton's Bat) and changes in their insect prey. However, other species were less tightly linked. These results suggest that species with more specialized diets, or stronger reliance on insects during breeding, are likely to be most at risk.

OTHER FACTORS

While we found some evidence for direct effects of changing insect abundance, populations of insectivorous species are likely influenced by multiple environmental factors that also impact insect populations (i.e. shared responses). In these cases, the declines we see in insects may act as early warning signals.

Call to action

Our results point to wider repercussions of insect declines, but also, reciprocally, the wider benefits of providing habitats for insects to thrive. Managing spaces, including gardens, parks, road verges and farms, to be insect friendly can support not only insects, but also the variety of insectivorous species that rely on them. Simple actions to reduce artificial light pollution can also help nocturnal insects, such as moths, which are really important food for many birds and bats.

This research is part of the DRUID project: <https://druidproject.org.uk/>

